

Image characterization by means of tapered moments

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Abstract

We propose a simple generalization of the ordinary moments (and related statistics such as skewness and kurtosis) by the use of a centred taper function. In contrast to the ordinary moments, which imply a sum (or integral) over an infinite domain, the tapered moments can be applied to truncated (windowed) images as well as images with extended wings, such as theoretical diffraction images. As a special case, the tapered first moment could be the same as Tukey's biweight centroid.

Document History

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1	0	2010-07-20	LL	Issued with minor changes mainly in the terminology ('windowed' changed to tapered', $W(z)$ to $T(z)$, etc)
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1 Motivation

In many circumstances it is desirable to characterize one- or two-dimensional images by means of a few parameters, such as the total flux, mean position, width, and skewness. In the two-dimensional case, additional parameters may for example describe the orientation of elongated images. In the following we only discuss one-dimensional continuous images $I(x)$, but the extension to several dimensions and/or discrete images is straightforward.

The ordinary image moments

$$M_k = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^k I(x) dx \quad (1)$$

provide a common and standard way of characterizing images: M_0 is the total intensity, $\bar{x} = M_1/M_0$ is the location of the centre of gravity, etc. Central moments are defined by

$$\mu_k = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (x - \bar{x})^k I(x) dx, \quad (2)$$

which after proper normalization provide measures of the width, skewness, kurtosis, etc of the image. By definition, $\mu_1 = 0$, which can also be regarded as a defining condition for \bar{x} .

The use of ordinary moments is problematic for two reasons. First, the observed images are usually truncated, for example, we only have samples within a finite window. If the intensity is not strictly zero outside of the window, the resulting moments become biased, and the bias will be sensitive to the exact location of the image within the window. Moreover, this sensitivity increases drastically for the higher moments, which therefore could become very unreliable.

The other problem is related to the convergence of integrals (or sums) such as Eq. (1) in the ideal cases when there is no truncation of the image. For example, the diffraction image for given pupil and wavefront errors can in principle be computed for arbitrarily large x , so truncation should not be a problem (at least in principle). However, diffraction wings tend to decrease as some finite negative power of x , which means that the moments become undefined or divergent above a certain degree. For example, a rectangular pupil produces diffraction wings $I(x) \propto x^{-2}$ for large x , which means that M_k is undefined for odd k and infinite for even $k > 1$. In particular, the centre of gravity is undefined and the RMS width is infinite. This makes the ordinary image moments unsuitable also for theoretical investigations (cf. Lindegren, LL-064).

2 Definition of tapered moments

A number of standard techniques exist for estimating e.g. the location (x_0) of a distribution in a robust way, that is, relatively insensitive to outliers which statistically represent the wings of the distribution. A certain class of robust location estimators can be defined in terms of a weighting

function $w(z)$, as discussed in Lindegren (LL-068):

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w\left(\frac{x-x_0}{s}\right) I(x) dx = 0, \quad (3)$$

where s is a scale parameter which determines how far out from the centroid we want to go. For example, Tukey's biweight (TBW) uses the weighting function

$$w(z) = \begin{cases} z(1-z^2)^2 & \text{if } |z| < 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

which means that no part of $I(x)$ with $x < x_0 - s$ or $x > x_0 + s$ will be used.

One can define a class of generalized central moments as

$$\mu_k = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (x-x_0)^k T\left(\frac{x-x_0}{s}\right) I(x) dx, \quad (5)$$

where the condition $\mu_1 = 0$ implicitly defines the centroid x_0 . Here, $T(z)$ is a fixed taper function gradually decreasing from 1 (at $z = 0$) to 0 at infinity, or beyond some finite $|z|$. For example, Tukey's biweight corresponds to the taper function

$$T(z) = \begin{cases} (1-z^2)^2 & \text{if } |z| < 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (6)$$

Another useful taper function might be the Gaussian $T(z) = \exp(-z^2/2)$.

The taper function $T(z)$ should be symmetric (even), non-negative for all z , and have finite moments

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} z^k T(z) dz \quad (7)$$

for all k . The Gaussian and Eq. (6) obviously satisfy these conditions. The parameter s may be chosen according to the situation, for example the number of samples available for computing the windowed moments. With a suitable choice of s , the tapered moments should be fairly insensitive to truncation effects.

In analogy with the ordinary moments, we may define the (tapered) standard width

$$\sigma = (\mu_2/\mu_0)^{1/2}, \quad (8)$$

skewness

$$\gamma_1 = \mu_3/\sigma^3, \quad (9)$$

and kurtosis

$$\gamma_2 = \mu_4/\sigma^4 - 3. \quad (10)$$

3 Conclusion

As is evident from Eq. (5), the tapered moments μ_k are just the ordinary central moments computed for the tapered image $T((x - x_0)/s)I(x)$. Thus, in the limit of large s , they approach the ordinary central moments of $I(x)$, if they exist. When the width of the taper function T approaches the width of the image itself, the interpretation of the moments becomes less clear, and in the limit of very small s the moments lose their meaning as a way of characterizing the image. Between these extremes, however, there is a regime where the tapered moments (width, skewness, etc) may provide a useful description of the images.

4 References

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